

IMPACT FACTORY

Reconciling demolition and deconstruction practices with circular building

Brecht Verstraete, Miet Vanheeswyck, Samuel Klein, Bob Geldermans

WIT architecten

‘WIT Architecten’ often operates at the overlap between urban planning and architecture, feeling at home in layered and mixed urban areas and undeterred by complex sites or an almost impossible set of preconditions. A thorough reading of the existing situation is always an essential part of the design process. What exists is systematically screened for latent qualities that can be magnified, supplemented, and complemented. For WIT, the context is the generator of a thorough search for self-evident and feasible solutions. The contribution to the (urban) landscape is crucial, and averse to wastefulness, boasting or ostentation.

INTRODUCTION

In 2022, WIT was selected as the designer for the ‘Impact Factory’ project in Mechelen. A private project company and the City of Mechelen are joining forces here with the aim of developing a hub around circular and impact entrepreneurship. The Impact Factory positions itself as the home base for a new type of entrepreneurship that demonstrates that doing good business and doing business for good can be perfectly complementary (Stadsmakersfonds and City of Mechelen, 2023).

Located centrally between the train station and the city center of Mechelen, the site includes a former industrial dry cleaning facility (De Potterij), an office building to be repurposed, a connecting coach house, and a limited building plot. This space will be designated for research, experimentation, co-creation, demonstration, and local production.

De Potterij will accommodate laboratory and studio spaces, as well as an event/workshop space. The office building will be transformed into an incubator for start-ups and scale-ups focused on the circular economy and impact entrepreneurship, with active support provided for the development of sustainable business models. The space will feature both individual and shared workspaces, laboratories, and event spaces.

The office building (1), Coach house (2), De Potterij (3) and a limited building plot (4) situated in a building block in the city center of Mechelen.

CHAPTER 1 POLICIES AND ATTITUDES

Exterior and interior impressions of the existing buildings. Photographed by Michiel de Cleene.

The desired net area of approximately 3.000 m² is to a large extent already available in the existing buildings. It tempts us to make a bold statement:

“The Impact Factory does not need to be built; it is already there!”

DESIGN STRATEGY

Several issues need to be resolved or clarified. To ensure maximum retention, a strategic approach is essential. Every intervention must initially improve what already exists and focus on it. A four-stepped plan was applied to achieve this:

A: Improving circulation

The existing structure of the office building already provides the required small, secluded workspaces and large studios that can be used collectively. However, the current layout features a long, dark, and confusing circulation route along the common walls, which feels cramped. From an urban planning reflex, the architects feel the need for a new 'main street' on the south façade, extending through the courtyard. The new circulation is more compact, but also more interesting and clearer.

The office building has been turned around: the former rear façade now becomes the new front. A wide extension along this façade is open and oriented outward. It strengthens the orientation and immediately improves the energy performance of the shell. This space is visible to everyone and connects the different levels in an alternative way.

B: A roof landscape and reserve for the future

The office building lacks a ground level. To provide the Impact Factory with an inspiring and usable outdoor space, the potential of the roofs is utilized: a raised ground level on the roof of the new front building and accessible areas on the roof of the existing office building are introduced.

The process begins with structurally reinforcing the most important roofs of the office building. A new beam grid is supported directly by the existing columns. This provides an optimal base layer for greenery, with sufficient topsoil, while relieving the burden on the underlying supporting structure. Additionally, it forms a potential reserve for future roof extensions. The new roof structure simultaneously serves as a load-bearing cantilever for the new 'main street' over the courtyard.

To create a fully-fledged outdoor area replacing the ground level, very good accessibility is essential. The roof must become a natural space to stay. Therefore, the new elevator is extended directly to the roof landscape, opening into a garden room at the top. This vantage point looks just over the immediate neighbors at the domes and towers of Mechelen. Conversely, as a 'lantern' it also serves to prominently position the Impact Factory on the urban map, visible from nearby buildings or from the public space.

IMPACT FACTORY

A: Improving circulation, B: A roof landscape and reserve for the future, C: Clarifying the distinct structure of the Potterij, D: A shared entrance, the front porch.

C: Clarifying the distinct structure of the Potterij

This building is only a small part of a former industrial complex. The rampant building conglomeration that overran the inside of the building block has illegibly split the urban tissue into several properties. The space is overwhelming and unclear at the same time.

A careful reading of the plan led the designers to make an intervention that is just as strategic as in the office building: by removing a section of the floor on the south side, the experience changes completely. What remains is a very special (twisted) square section spanning two floors, supported by a central column, and a compact, column-free building volume of three floors on the east side.

Removing the floor on the south side of the Potterij. Photographed by WIT architecten.

The 'armpit' in the southwest then becomes an interplay of interior and exterior spaces, of walled and sunlit double-height spaces cascading from the ground floor to the roof. A new staircase and elevator naturally find their place here. The new 'patio' is a bright, inviting place along the ground floor routing, which halves the passage length and encourages exploration.

D: A shared entrance, the front porch

There is some open terrain on ground level, which is the only place where a decent tree can grow. It would be a shame to build on that plot. This raised the question: is a simple, common 'front porch' sufficient as a shared entrance space and front garden? The front porch is at the same time garden, gate, hall, garage, terrace, courtyard. It seems crucial to find a good balance between enclosing and opening, between sheltering and making accessible.

The entrance to the Impact Factory faces what will become a square in the future. The rhythm of the columns guides the promenade on the square, leading along closed, semi-open and open parts that mark the main entrance. One enters the vestibule through a portico that embraces the site. Three façades surround this courtyard and provide access to the various building parts. The structure defines the Impact Factory, provides a face and forms the parapet for the terrace on the first floor.

These various interventions speak the same architectural language. While they offer clarity, accessibility, and address functional needs, they simultaneously foster a sense of unity and continuity across the collection of buildings. However, the leading role remains reserved for the existing buildings, whose distinct characteristics shape the fundamental spatial expressions.

METHODS

The Impact Factory is ideally an open-ended project. Each temporary intervention is tested for necessity, flexibility, and adaptability. For this reason, interventions are designed to be as demountable as possible. The goal is not to maximize implementation prematurely but to focus on interventions that support optimal future operability.

S-layers and R-strategies

This work adopts the principles of Frank Duffy and Stewart Brand, the so-called ‘shearing layers of change’ (Duffy, 1992; Brand, 1994). These shearing layers (S-layers) help to read and dissect buildings into components with different usage patterns and turnover rates. This is essential to anticipate the most optimal circular strategies and reuse routes. The latter strategies and routes are widely referred to as the ‘R-strategies’, and nowadays fairly established at Belgian and European level (Watkins and Meysner, 2022; Bocken et al., 2016; Potting et al., 2017). When linked, these two – S and R – tools form a powerful matrix of possible and probable material and product flows (Geldermans, 2016).

The matrix indicates a methodology on three levels:

Refuse and Rethink

As discussed in the previous sections, this method involved refusing large-scale demolition and rethinking the existing conditions and spatial layout. The approach prioritized highly targeted demolition and the integration of subtle additions to adapt and optimize the design.

Redesign and Reuse

The existing buildings were once designed and considered finished. In the current approach, the buildings are being reused and redesigned with a deliberate open end, a spatial framework for the program that is currently required, but allowing future adaptability. This design perspective views the existing buildings as a bank of space and materials.

Reapplying and Repurposing

A third level of the methodology focuses on reapplying and repurposing materials sourced from external locations. During the design process, opportunities came our way from unexpected and unknown angles. In some cases, research was conducted into materials from projects that came on our radar and that were going to be demolished in the near future. In other instances, specific materials were sought proactively; materials that were likely to become available and align seamlessly with the design requirements.

Spacebook

To visualize design choices and options and maintain an overview, a spacebook was developed. It is a collection of standardized images of each prominent or typical room in the interior. These images gradually mature throughout the design process, are continually shaped by internal discussions within the design team and dialogues with the client; and, if possible, with the users. Furthermore, they serve as a communication tool with the contractor during the implementation phase.

DESIGN AND MATERIALIZATION OUTCOMES

The steel window frames being reclaimed from a nearby demolition site in Mechelen. Storage of the window frames and design exercise for positioning of the reclaimed frames in the front façade.

Reuse on-site

An initial screening of the reuse inventory was conducted by the design team. Several materials will be given a second life, on site, in the new project. For instance, the herringbone parquet will be freshened up again, radiators will be recovered, and many interior doors will be retained. For other materials with reuse potential, selective disassembly was planned for the demolition and deconstruction phase. These materials can be temporarily stored in a warehouse provided by the client for this purpose. During the construction stage, efforts will focus on finding new applications for these materials, as well as developing a methodology for their transport, storage, pricing, and market setting.

Resources from other project sites

A notable example is the integration of the steel exterior window frames from the old library in Mechelen into the new façade. To apply these reclaimed window frames accurately, specific information and documentation were required, which only the original manufacturer could provide. Fortunately, the original manufacturer was willing and able to proactively engage with the project. Solutions were found through collaboration between the manufacturer and the project team (designers, developers, the client, and material experts). Subsequently, the design was adjusted accordingly. These adjustments included recoating the frames, replacing the glazing and outer cover strips, but also making decisions related to construction and composition, such as measures to control the propagation of fire.

Following the cleanup of the cemetery in the city of Mechelen, we were asked if we could do something with old gravestones in bluestone. A bit surprised at first by the lugubrious offer, inspiration was drawn from Pikionis who in 1951 constructed the pathway to the Acropolis in Athens using natural stone from Athenian architectural heritage that was demolished in the 1950s. Disgusted by the atrocity of the Greek authorities, he made the destroyed historical heritage part of the new landscape of the Acropolis (Malawski, 2017). Similarly, with minimal effort and processing, the old gravestones can be repurposed as paving in the garden of the Impact Factory.

On the slopes of the acropolis by Mayte Piera.

For a long time, a suitable recuperated or biobased material was sought for the renovation of the façade in the courtyard that matched the aesthetic requirements. A project in Leuven scheduled for demolished has the ideal reflecting aluminum corrugated sheets that fit within the design of the courtyard. An additional advantage is that the corrugated sheets cover a closed façade surface and can therefore be transferred to the Impact Factory as complete sheets without openings and cuttings. The client is talking with the developer of the demolition project to reach an agreement for the careful dismantling of the façade panels. Together with the contractor and producers, it remains to be explored how these panels can be repurposed for a new life in our courtyard.

Finally, reclaimed materials with clear reuse potential are often found in finishing layers. Tiles and wooden flooring for instance are now widely available. A specification outlining the required standards and appearance was drawn up. In collaboration with the contractor, the most suitable options will be identified and integrated into the design during the subsequent stages of the construction process.

DISCUSSION AND REFLECTION

The design of the Impact Factory embodies the concept of 'collage architecture,' a renovation approach that integrates both new and old materials, drawing directly from the context and in turn giving context to a subsequent use.

Working with used materials requires a different approach from the design team. It requires expertise in assessing usability, employing specific disassembly techniques to carefully extract materials from their original locations, and ensuring their workability to meet functional or aesthetic requirements associated with their new use. Challenges related to the pricing, transport, and storage logistics of reclaimed materials remain significant. The warehouse that was made available by the client for the temporary storage of reclaimed materials during the design process has significantly made matters easier.

For the implementation of the reclaimed materials, the architect must become a master builder again and be advised and assisted by contractors and reuse dealers at an early stage - when selecting the materials. This implies the return to a qualitative and close collaboration between client, contractor, manufacturer and architect with an artisanal dynamic.

Study model of the new façades.

The architect takes on the
role of an artisan,
The contractor acts a bit
like an architect,
And the client embraces the
flexibility of the final result.

A form of collaboration in a design-and-build framework appears to be the most suitable. There are many opportunities for the reuse of materials that may currently escape our attention. Combining forces, knowledge and connections to create an optimal link between demand, supply and application of reuse materials is indispensable for reconciling demolition and deconstruction practices with circular building. By involving the contractor at an early stage in the design choices and options, specific opportunities and technical feasibility can be sought in a faster way, whilst increasing the level of viability of innovative solutions.

Simultaneously, flexibility is expected from the architect throughout the entire design and construction process. Every time new opportunities pop up, details must be rethought, without losing the original key flavors of the design. Being open to the unexpected and letting go of the strict control over the design requires a different attitude than the traditional role of the architect.

REFERENCES

1. Stadsmakersfonds and City of Mechelen (2023). Impact Factory information dossier market exploration. Available from <https://www.impactfactory.be/home/> (accessed 22 August 2024).
2. Duffy, F. and Hannay, P. (1992) *The changing workplace*. New York: Phaidon Press.
3. Brand, S. (1994) *How buildings learn - What happens after they are built*. New York: Viking Press.
4. Watkins, E. and Meysner, A. (2022) 'European Circular Economy policy landscape overview', Re-port, Institute for European Environmental Policy , Brussels; Belgium.
5. Bocken, N.M., De Pauw, I., Bakker, C. and Van Der Grinten, B. (2016) 'Product design and business model strategies for a circular economy,' *Journal of Industrial and Production Engineering*, 33(5), pp.308–320. doi:10.1080/21681015.2016.1172124.
6. Potting, J., Hekkert, M.P., Worrell, E. and Hanemaaijer, A. (2017) *Circular Economy: Measuring innovation in the product chain*. Available from: <https://dspace.library.uu.nl/handle/1874/358310> (accessed 21 August 2024).
7. Geldermans, R.J. (2016) *Design for Change and Circularity – Accommodating Circular Material & Product Flows in Construction*, *Energy Procedia*, 96, pp. 301-311. Doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2016.09.153.
8. Braungart, M. and McDonough, W. (2002) *Cradle to Cradle: Remaking the way we make things*. Berkeley: North Point Press.
9. Rau, T., and Oberhuber, S. (2022). *Material Matters: Developing Business for a Circular Economy* (1st ed.). Routledge. Doi: 10.4324/9781003258674.
10. Gept, B., Meex, E., Nuyts, E., Knapen, E., Verbeeck, G. (2019) 'Existing databases as means to explore the potential of the building stock as material bank', *IOP Conf. SER.: Earth Environ. Sci.* 225 012002. Doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/225/1/01200.
11. Malawski, K. (2017) "'Pikionis' Pathway: Paving the Acropolis', *The Architectural League of New York*. Available from: <https://archleague.org/article/pikionis-pathway-paving-acropolis/> (accessed 21 August 2024).

Practices in Research #05 - Demolitions and Deconstructions - December 2024

Online Open Access Double-Blind Peer-Reviewed Journal for Practice-Based Research in Architecture

Editor in Chief: Harold Fallon (KU Leuven, AgwA)

Associate Editors: Benoît Burquel (ULB, AgwA), Benoit Vandenbulcke (ULiège, AgwA)

Editorial Advisors: Juliane Greb (UAntwerpen, Büro Juliane Greb), Urszula Kozminska (Arkitektskolen Aarhus), Bie Plevoets (UHasselt, As Found Network)

Editorial Board : Martina Barcellona Corte (ULiège), Benoît Burquel (ULB, AgwA), Johan De Walsche (UAntwerpen), Christine Fontaine (UCLouvain), Harold Fallon (KU Leuven, AgwA), Juliane Greb (UAntwerpen, Büro Juliane Greb), Wouter Van Acker (ULB), Benoit Vandenbulcke (ULiège, AgwA)

Scientific Committee: Pier Vittorio Aureli (EPFL, Dogma), Ido Avissar (EAV&T Paris Est, List), Lisa De Visscher (ULiège, A+ Architecture), Arnaud Hendrickx (KU Leuven), Nikolaus Hirsch (CIVA), Karen Kesteloot (KU Leuven, Studio Bont), Eric Le Coguiet (ULiège), Paul Lewis (Princeton, LTL architects), Cédric Libert (ENSASE), Emilie Morales (ULB, Morales-Finch), Jarrik Ouburg (HOH Architecten), Martin Outers (UCLouvain, Matador), Claus Peder Pederson (Arkitektskolen Aarhus), Alex Renderos (UCA), Robin Schaeveerbeek (KU Leuven), Xavier Van Rooyen (ULiège), Caroline Voet (KU Leuven, Voet Architectuur)

Double-blind peer review process : www.architectureinpractice.eu/pirjournal

Front and back cover images : © ARCH+, Summacumfemmer, büero Juliane Greb

Thanks to Orfée Grandhomme & Ismaël Bennani

Practices in Research is published under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License and fulfils the DOAJ definition of Open Access. Practices in Research provides immediate Open Access to its content on the principle that making research freely available to the public supports a greater global exchange of knowledge. Copyright for articles published in this journal is retained by the authors without restriction. By appearing in this Open-Access journal, the content of the articles are free to be used in any setting by third parties, with proper attribution.

ISSN: 2736-3996

Practices in Research Journal
Rue des Palais 153 - 1030 Brussels
T. +32 (0)2 244 44 35
info@architectureinpractice.eu
www.architectureinpractice.eu/pirjournal

In Practice
interuniversity research group
of practising architects

Scientific
Research
Network

Universiteit
Antwerpen

